

The current role of Artificial Intelligence in public health: A scoping review

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Acknowledgement and disclaimer

This project is funded by the National Institute for Health and Care Research Public Health Research Programme (NIH175419).

The views expressed are those of the author(s) and not necessarily those of the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

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1. Background

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a broad field encompassing various techniques, including machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision (1). AI, which refers to algorithms integrated into systems and tools, learns from data to be able to perform automated tasks without explicit human programming (2-4).

AI is particularly useful for tasks requiring pattern recognition, prediction, and data analysis (5). In healthcare, for instance, AI applications have been used to enhance image analysis, streamline operations, enable personalized and predictive healthcare, and support clinical decision-making (6). In public health, AI has been used for spatial modelling, risk prediction, misinformation control, public health surveillance, disease forecasting, and epidemic and pandemic modelling (5). Additionally, conversational AI interventions have been used to support smoking cessation (7) and reducing alcohol intake (8), and AI-assisted apps have been used to improve exercise technique (9). Other uses of AI in public health remain hypothesised but un- or under-explored in practice, for instance in public communication (10).

The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, highlighted both the challenges and opportunities for using AI in public health. The scale and severity of the pandemic underscored the need for more efficient and effective interventions, and AI was used for disease surveillance, contact tracing, combating misinformation, predicting transmission patterns, and forecasting disease spread (5).

While the theoretical groundwork for machine learning and deep learning was laid in the 1980s, recent advancements in computing power and the development of large language models like OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini have sparked renewed interest in AI. These models, with more user-friendly interfaces and general-purpose applications, offer the potential to help tackle a wide range of problems (11).

However, even if AI-assisted interventions in public health are shown to be effective, there are nonetheless barriers to the adoption of AI. These include public trust, health equity, ethical considerations, data privacy concerns, and the need for training and expertise to use AI effectively ([4](#), [10](#), [12](#), [13](#)).

Given the potential scale of use of AI, there is a need to regularly examine how AI-assisted interventions have been, are being, and could be used in public health contexts. To better understand and guide the potential use of AI in public health, we will conduct five linked reviews. The first three reviews will assess the effectiveness of AI-assisted interventions for reducing engagement with smoking, drinking alcohol, and physical inactivity. **The fourth review will summarize current AI applications in health surveillance and policy decisions.** The fifth review will explore the potential role of AI in public health, including potential benefits and challenges. To help maximise the utility of these reviews for a UK setting, only studies considering AI in high-income countries will be included. Additionally, all reviews will have a focus on health equity, particularly concerning inequities in access or use to AI-assisted interventions.

These reviews aim to inform public health professionals about the practical applications and most promising options for using AI in public health.

This protocol corresponds to the fourth review: the current AI applications in health surveillance and policy decisions.

2. Review Aim

The present reviews will systematically synthesise evidence from primary studies, reviews, opinion pieces, and editorials around the use of AI in public health in high-income countries to address the following question:

1. What is the current role of AI in health surveillance and policy decision making

3. Methods

This scoping review will be conducted with reference to the JBI updated methodological guidance for scoping reviews ([14](#)), and the protocol is reported with reference to JBI best practice guidance and reporting items for the development of scoping review protocols ([15](#)).

3.1. Patient and Public Involvement (PPI)

We will undertake a programme of patient and public involvement (PPI) with relevant stakeholder groups. There will be three phases of engagement ([Table 1](#)). First will be engagement in protocol refinement and confirmation, with a primary focus on specifying the inclusion criteria and clarifying the definition of key constructs related to: AI and its sub-domains; and the remit of public health that will be considered. Second will be engagement to provide feedback on preliminary and final synthesis findings. Third will be engagement on the development of implications for research, policy and practice.

We will undertake PPI with three UK wide communities of practice. Two of these communities are from NIHR funded research infrastructures:

- **NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):** The NIHR has funded thirty HDRCs that aim to boot research capacity and capability within local government. They aim to embed a culture of using evidence in decision-making and to understand how decision impact on health and health inequalities. These

collaborations have the potential to use AI in their public health decision-making and practice.

- **NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):** Teams provide timely and accessible evaluations of public health interventions to Local Authorities. Evaluations have, or intend to, examine interventions that have used AI.
- **Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:** The hub comprises an AI network of over 300 office members that works to discuss AI risks, rewards and readiness in local government across the UK.

At each of these three phases we will host two online meetings, comprising a mixture of professionals from the three communities of practice. Combining professionals will hopefully spark dynamic and challenging discussion, while hosting two meetings will aim to maximise attendance.

3.2. Approach to Searching and Data Sources

One AI search facet will be used, which draws upon published and unpublished AI search filters either created by members of the InterTASC (Technology Appraisal Support Collaboration) Information Specialists' Sub-Group (ISSG) or hosted on the associated ISSG Search Filter Resource ([16](#)).

The search will combine the AI facet with broad public health terms as well as those reflecting activities linked to the research question, such as policy making and surveillance. These terms have been derived from iterative searching, with keywords and MeSH terms harvested from relevant papers and reference lists. No study design filter will be used, but a date limit from 01 January 2020 onwards will be added.

We will conduct searches in: Medline (Ovid); Embase (Ovid); Web of Science; and Scopus. Searches of Web of Science and Scopus will be undertaken to take advantage of their multi-disciplinary coverage, given the technological focus of the topic. Additionally,

we will conduct supplementary literature searching as determined by the needs of each review, which may include checking reference lists, citation tracking, contacting authors, and web searching for unpublished material and policy documents.

The search strategy for Medline for is presented in [Supplement A](#).

3.3. Eligibility Criteria

The overall eligibility criteria are presented in [Table 2](#). These may be refined with stakeholders during the first phase of PPI.

Interventions must be AI tools or systems that are being used, or were used, for outbreak detection, early warning, trend prediction, or public health response modelling or assessment. Interventions must be in local authority or national public health contexts, not healthcare settings or other contexts.

Included studies must be set in, or relevant to, high-income countries, as defined by the [World Bank](#). Included studies must also be in English language.

3.4. Study Screening Methods

Titles and abstracts from the search will be screened independently and in duplicate by two members of the review team. References included by at least one reviewer on eligibility assessment will progress to full-text screening.

Full texts of references will be independently screened by two reviewers. References identified through other means, such as reference checking and citation searching, will undergo duplicate title and abstract screening as above.

Conflicts in assessment will be resolved through discussion and recourse to a third member of the review team.

3.5. Software

Retrieved study reports from the data sources will be exported to Endnote 21, where they will be combined and de-duplicated. They will then be uploaded to Rayyan platform for title and abstract screening, and Microsoft Excel will be used for full text screening and data extraction.

3.6. Quality Appraisal

The rationale for quality appraisal of study reports is to assess clarity and transparency of reporting; methodological rigour in the research process; robustness in the findings, including robustness in any claims to generalisability; and compliance with ethical standards. Nonetheless, we expect to include evidence from diverse studies, often without participants, where quality appraisal will likely be of limited use, and therefore will not conduct quality appraisal in this review.

3.7. Number of Reviewers

One member of the review team will lead information specialist activities related to study report retrieval (JK). Six members of the review team will undertake screening, extraction, and appraisal (SH; JK; RE; GM-T; SL; RA). The remainder of the review team will serve as arbiters of decision conflicts in study screening, support the synthesis of findings, and develop the final funder recommendations.

3.8. Data Extraction and Coding

We will extract data for:

- Study identification: method of study identification; first author; publication year; title

- Study characteristics and methodology: country; setting; data collection year(s); study design; data collection method; analysis method; outcome measure timing and reliability
- Public health context: area and context of public health activities
- Intervention: how AI was or is used; context of AI usage; modality and type of AI; alternative to AI previously or currently used; other relevant information about the use of AI
- Outcome data: performance of AI, including direct outcomes (for example, time to outbreak detection or early warning, accuracy of trend prediction), indirect outcomes (lives saved, diseases prevented), and acceptability of the AI tool among public health workers and the public; any other relevant outcome data

Additional data in each review may be extracted depending on the needs of the review.

3.9. Synthesis

Broad summaries of how AI has been or is being used in public health will be reported. The exact organisation of evidence will be determined once the studies have been identified and extracted, but will likely be structured by the type of intervention: outbreak detection, early warning, trend prediction, or public health response modelling or assessment. Within each type of intervention, we will report on the studies that have used, or are using, AI, including the performance of the intervention (if reported).

We will highlight health equity considerations, with reference to PROGRESS-Plus characteristics ([17](#)). Specifically, we will report any findings from studies highlighting how use of AI has impacted upon health equity.

3.10. Synthesis Output

Key characteristics of all included studies will be reported in summary tables. If possible, we will develop infographics to present the results of each review question. Finally, to

support future intervention research and practice in this field, we will report on implications for research, policy, and practice.

3.11. Certainty of Evidence

We will not assess the certainty of evidence.

4. Ethics

Ethical approval for these reviews will not be required. PPI consultation with stakeholder groups will be conducted in accordance with any ethical requirements stipulated by the organisations and research studies that recruit participating members.

5. Discussion

This review will inform thinking around how AI could be best used in public health by summarising the existing evidence for how AI has been or is being used in public health contexts.

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Table 1. Stakeholder Engagement in Review Process

Review Stage	Stakeholder Groups	Identification of Stakeholders	Aims of Engagement
Development and confirmation of protocol	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>Northern Ireland does not currently have a funded HDRC.</p> <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	Refine inclusion criteria through definition of key concepts (for example, AI, public health).
Refinement and confirmation of preliminary and final findings	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	Provide feedback on preliminary findings. Refine and confirm final findings.
Development and confirmation of recommendations and dissemination strategy	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	<p>Generate implications for policy, practice and research.</p> <p>Refine and confirm dissemination strategy. Ensuring findings are accessible to intended audience.</p>

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

	Included	Excluded
Population	Any	
Setting	High-income countries, as defined by the World Bank	Middle- and lower-income countries
Context	Local authority and national public health contexts	Healthcare, clinical and other contexts
Intervention	AI tools that are being used, or were used, for outbreak detection, early warning, trend prediction, or public health response modelling or assessment. AI is broadly defined as algorithms integrated into systems and tools that can learn from data to be able to perform automated tasks without explicit human programming.	Other interventions, including how AI tools could be used in public health contexts
Outcomes	Outcomes associated with the performance of the AI tool, including direct outcomes (for example, time to outbreak detection or early warning, accuracy of trend prediction), indirect outcomes (lives saved, diseases prevented), and acceptability of the AI tool among public health workers and the public	Other outcomes
Language	English	Other languages
Date of publication	01 January 2020 to present	
Study design	Experimental or observational studies, editorials, commentaries	Other study designs, including reviews and modelling studies where the intervention was not trialled in practice
Publication type	Published or preprint	Conference abstracts

Supplement A: Search Strategies (Medline)

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL (initial search dates [will be updated]: 1946 to July 15, 2025)

#	Query	Results
1	exp artificial intelligence/	243,836
2	exp Machine Learning/	98,411
3	(AI or AI4H).ti,ab.	76,708
4	("comput* intelligence" or "comput* reasoning" or "machine intelligence" or "artificial intelligence" or "natural language processing" or llm*1 or "large language model*" or "language learning model*" or "classification algorithm*" or "computer heuristic*" or "convolutional network*" or "expert system*" or "recommender system*" or "decision support system*" or "decision tree" or "deep learning" or "data science" or "feature detection" or "generative pre-trained transformer" or "generative pretrained transformer" or "learning algorithm*" or "machine learning" or "neural net*" or "reinforcement learning" or "*supervised learning" or "intelligent agent*").ti,ab,kf.	401,429
5	("boltzmann machine*" or "long short-term memory" or "gated recurrent unit*" or "rectified linear unit*" or autoencoder or "auto-encoder" or backpropagation or "multilayer perceptron" or "multi-layer perceptron" or convnet or "convolutional learning").ti,ab,kf.	21,765
6	("Bing chat" or ChatGPT* or "Chat GPT" or "Google* Bard" or "Google* Gemini" or "IBM Watson" or "Microsoft* Bing" or "Microsoft* Copilot" or OpenAI or "Open AI" or PathAI or "Path AI" or DALL-E or invideo or Claude).ti,ab,kf.	9,162
7	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6	526,188
8	exp *Public Health/	2,224,593
9	public health/	101,415
10	public health.ti,kf.	141,248
11	public health.ab. /freq=2	57,059
12	exp Population Health/	41,443
13	exp Primary Prevention/	195,967

14	((local or regional) adj (government* or authori* or council*)).ti,ab.	14,277
15	exp *Health Promotion/	58,533
16	8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15	2,539,822
17	(evaluat* or decide* or decision* or case stud*).ti.	890,612
18	("policy maker*" or policymaker* or "policy making" or policymaking).ti,kf.	3,703
19	(policy or policies).ab. /freq=3	47,581
20	Policy Making/	18,558
21	Public Policy/	34,334
22	17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21	978,127
23	exp Population Surveillance/	75,714
24	(infodemiology or infoveillance).ti,kf.	836
25	(misinformation or disinformation).ti.	2,119
26	Infodemiology/	85
27	exp *Disease Outbreaks/sn [Statistics & Numerical Data]	7,016
28	Disease Outbreaks/pc [Prevention & Control]	17,872
29	Foodborne Diseases/pc [Prevention & Control]	2,696
30	*Foodborne Diseases/ep [Epidemiology]	2,416
31	((prevent* or monitor* or control or surveillance or model?ing or forecast* or predict*) adj2 (outbreak* or pandemic* or epidemic*)).ti.	3,046
32	Health Policy/	75,526
33	23 or 24 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32	177,181
34	22 or 33	1,133,902
35	7 and 16 and 34	3,839
36	limit 35 to yr="2020 -Current"	1,684
37	Public health.ti,kf.	141,248
38	*artificial intelligence/ or *large language model/	34,790
39	(artificial intelligence or AI or llm* or machine learning or deep learning or expert system*).ti,kf.	196,106
40	38 or 39	210,509
41	37 and 40	1,004
42	limit 41 to yr="2020 -Current"	934
43	36 or 42	2,496